

How to Ping Pong? - Designing and tutoring an Online international introductory course

A view from a tutor

Introductory course for the joint two-year master program “Roads to Democracy(ies)”, using Ping Pong, a Learning Management System (LMS)
University of Uppsala and University of Coimbra

Resume

During the scholarly years of 2005/06 and 2006/07, the University of Uppsala and the University of Coimbra had a joint two-year master program “Roads to Democracy(ies)”, conceived according to Tuning educational principles.

In this master, the students can choose if they want to exchange university in the second semester. The students, who choose to exchange, have in the first semester an extra seminar, a common online introductory course, using a Learn Management System (LMS) - Ping Pong. In the third and fourth semester, students have to write their thesis. The main goal of the common online seminar is to put students from the two countries working together and sharing knowledge.

In this article, we are going to provide a description, step by step, of what we have done to design the introductory course of the master program “Roads to Democracy(ies)”, using Ping Pong, a Learning Management System (LMS).

Furthermore, we will be going to discuss the decisions we made about usability and design of the course. Our main goal is to provide a manual of best practices in how to setup an online class.

What is Ping Pong?

Ping Pong is a Learning Management System (LMS) used in University of Uppsala and it was the chosen LMS to work with in the online seminar. As any LMS, Ping Pong follows some principles in its sections. There is a section where the main course is designed, a section of communication, a section about the LMS, a section to save and share documents and a section of organizer and notes.

Ping Pong has three roles of users: administrator, teacher or tutor and student. As a student, the user can only view the content of the course and he is not allowed to make any changes in the main section of the course. The contributions of the student are based in

communication, like discussion forums, instant messaging and email, and in the possibility to share documents in a specific section.

As a teacher or tutor, the user have access to every options in the LMS. It is permitted to the teacher/tutor to design the course, make changes and to view the statistics of the system, tracking the the movements of the students. The administrator has the power of create and manage accounts of the users.

Getting started

First, we get acquainted with Ping Pong. We study the Guide of the LMS and we tried and explored the possibilities of the web application by inserting text, by sending messages (PIMs - Ping Pong instant messages) to ourselves, by creating new folders and documents and by testing calendar events. Beside the account of tutor that was given to us, we asked for a student account, to know what students see and what they can access.

It is important to tutors to have a student account because a student account has some limits. Knowing what students can and cannot do makes easier to respond to their questions, in the technical area.

According to Pallof & Pratt, "three basic steps are involved in creating an effective syllabus for an online course: (1) defining outcomes and objectives, (2) choosing appropriate reading material, and (3) establishing a topic-driven course outline"¹.

Then, we erased all this and began to think in a structure for the course in Ping Pong, based on the structure that Professors gave us [Attachment 1].

This steps were inserted in the main section of the Ping Pong, the "Content Menu" section, which was chosen to insert the contents of the course.

Before the course begins, students must be aware of the content of the course. This means that the tutor must design, based on the teachers information, the whole course before it starts.

In this section, we had created nine sub-sections:

- **Introduction**, which function is to welcome the students and to provide information about the outcomes and the competencies students must acquire at the end of the course. This way

¹ Rena M. Pallof and Keith Pratt, Building Learning Communities in Cyberspace: Effective Strategies for the Online Classroom, (San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers, 1999), 88.

the students can have an idea about what is expected and this way they can plan their study and make their own evaluation.

One of the implications for Online Learning that derived from the Behaviorist School of Learning, according to Mohames Ally, is that "learners should be told the explicit outcomes of the learning so that they can set expectations and can judge for themselves whether or not they have achieved the outcome of the online lesson"²

Introduction was the chosen section to provide some instructions about the tasks that students must complete during the course and to provide some practical instructions about the required reading and how to find the obligatory books on the web stores.

The University of Uppsala has an official procedure about the papers of students being checked in order to minimize plagiarism, so this kind of information was inserted in Introduction as well.

Beyond this and because we are dealing with students that were using an LMS for the first time, we felt necessary to insert a presentation of the features of the LMS. We use pictures of the icons of the application in order to explain what students can do in each section.

We inserted in Introduction a sub-section where we create a table in HTML language with a schematic form of the course that had been done by the teachers. In this table, we have the learning outcomes, the educational activities topic-driven and the assessment for each week of work that were developed in the next sections of the Content Menu.

Once the objectives have been determined, the next step is to create an effective syllabus, including topics for discussion, expectations for participation, and ways the class will be evaluated; a detailed outline describing the topics to be presented or discussed in the course in each class is unnecessary. Instead, broad topic headings give students a general idea of what will be considered and discussed in the course. The syllabus in the online classroom should be more open, allowing students more leeway for exploration. We have found that the most successful classes are guided by a syllabus that is topic-driven. In other words, the weekly "schedule" for the class includes a discussion topic for the week, with readings geared to spark discussion of that topic.³

Because this Introductory Course had presence seminars, the structure found was to give a topic each other week, alternating online discussion topics with face-to-face seminars.

This table had the expected time that teachers thought that students must spare with each task, but were decided that it was better not to give this information to the students, in

² Mohamed Ally, "Foundations of Educational Theory for Online Learning," in *Theory and Practice of Online Learning*, ed. Terry Anderson & Fathi Elloumi (Athabasca University, 2004), 8, http://cde.athabascau.ca/online_book/pdf/TPOL_book.pdf (accessed March 20, 2006)

³ Rena M. Palloff and Keith Pratt, *Building Learning Communities in Cyberspace: Effective Strategies for the Online Classroom*, (San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers, 1999), 88.

order to not influence the time that each student give to each task. Each student has is own time to learn new things so this way we do not force an equal time per task to all students.

- **Learn about the LMS**, which function is to teach the students how to work with the application. Because we are dealing with students that are not used to working with a LMS, this section is fundamental to provide guidelines and *how to's* for the technical tools. In order to motivate the students to work from the beginning, teachers assume this section as the first assignment. In this section, the student is required to make an online presentation of him self and to fill in the profile section with information and a picture. This kind of task has two goals. Besides to teach students to work and to explore the web application, this task provides a way to students and teachers get to know each other. The photograph is important because this way people can associate a face to a name.

*The first task of the e-learning teacher is to develop a sense of trust and safety within the electronic community. In the absence of this trust, learners will feel uncomfortable and constrained in posting their thoughts and comments. We usually facilitate this trust information by having students post a series of introductory comments about themselves.*⁴

We introduced in this section some step by step how to's with screenshots of the LMS and instructions how to fill in the profile section [Figure 1 of the attachment 2] and how to view the profile of the other students and teachers [Figure 2 of the attachment 2].

In this assignment, students and teachers must post a message about themselves in discussion forum that allows people to socialize, to know and to welcome each other, which is very important in this kind of medium.

- **Breaking the ice**, the second assignment, has a task that has a main function of stimulating students to search the web and libraries in order to gathering information about a topic. Because during the course, students must search in internet some issues, this is an important task to accomplish. This course has students and teachers from two countries so this section has two quizzes about democracy in each of them. This way students improved their skills of searching, get to know the other country democracy and they can discuss the issues of the quizzes with their fellows or the teachers from the other country.

These two assignments were not evaluated by the technical quality of the presentations, rather the active participation. This way, students can feel free to test and explore the LMS, as a new learning environment.

⁴ Terry Anderson, "Teaching in an Online Learning Context," in *Theory and Practice of Online Learning*, ed. Terry Anderson & Fathi Elloumi (Athabasca University, 2004), 280, http://cde.athabascau.ca/online_book/pdf/TPOL_book.pdf (accessed March 20, 2006)

- **Assignment 3, 4 and 5** are the assignments about the subject of the introductory course. In each of these assignments, there are three items: one with the specific outcomes and objectives for each assignment; one with the tasks and deadlines and other with some questions to begin the discussion of the topic.

Each assignment has a Reading List section with books, on line articles and general on line references. In these sub-sections, we put links to libraries of Universities of the two countries, links to on line books, to the sites where students can search the articles and to the general sites. We decided to let students search the articles instead of give them the direct link to the article in order to improve their search skills.

Besides, and as the two firsts assignments, these sub-sections had links to the discussion forums, that are the most important sections to construct the knowledge by the students.

- **Final work**, the sixth assignment has, besides the information about the task itself, a discussion forum as the other assignments, because this final work consists in presenting a thesis project proposal, which can and must be discussed by students. In this assignment, students must upload their thesis proposal into another section of the LMS, and because this is a new move inside the application we felt important to construct a *how to*, with screenshots, in order to guide the students, as shown in Picture 2 of the Attachment 2.

- **Evaluation** was inserted in Content Menu section with the function of give final feedback to students about their assessment.

- **Evaluation Form** is the last section of the Content Menu and it function is to provide feedback from the students in order to tutors and teachers improve the course.

Once the Content Menu was created, we had to think about where the activity takes place. In Ping Pong, as in any LMS, communication is the most important section, in what concerns to development and construction of the knowledge by the students. In the Contact Section of the LMS, students have several sub-sections where to get help and discuss the topics of the course.

- **Message Board** has the function to provide new information or to get the attention of the students for an important item. We used this section to provide information about changes in calendar activities, information about seminars that students must attend to, information about students moving to other country in the second semester and to provide some useful information about search and use web material that we felt necessary students to have like **how to know if the information on a website is reliable and how to cite on line references**. The search for information on the web can be very stressful and students, and even teachers, can feel overwhelming with information, so one important issue is to give tools and

knowledge about how to select the information that ones need and which information can be reliable.

Another issue, and because we are dealing with students mainly used to search information on books, is how to cite references from websites.

This kind of information was given pointing references online, if teachers or tutors create this kind of information they can inserted as documents in Reference section and allow students to see it or download it to their computers.

- **Frequently Asked Questions [FAQ]** is a sub-section where teachers or tutors put questions and answers that they feel pertinent or that a student asked and the teacher or tutor think that there might be another student with the same question.

- **Discussion** was the section where tutors and teachers created the discussion forums. There is a discussion forum to each assignment with a direct link from the Content Menu, since the tasks were based on active participation of the students.

The first discussion forum had the presentations of the students, teachers and tutors. This is the right place to tutors and teachers welcome the students and make them feel integrated in this new environment of learning. So answer to the students presentations, welcome them and answer their questions providing feedback, even at small things like just say hello, at this first meeting, is crucial to gain the student fidelity to the course.

- **Ping Pong Instant Messages [PIM]** is a synchronous communication type provided by this LMS. Beside asynchronous communication of the discussion forums it is important to use instant messaging in order to minimize the geographical distance between students. This kind of communication is more informal so it fits the need of students and teachers to socialize.

Picture a classroom on a college campus. As the time for class approaches, students begin to gather. They may arrive individually or in small groups. They begin to talk to each other, possibly about activities, friends, and life outside the classroom. When class ends, students gather again in the hallways, on the grounds of the campus, or in the student union in order to make personal connections, create friendships, and simply to socialize. In the computer-mediated classroom, as it is configured currently, instructors and students are represented by text on a screen [...]

Because students missed this socialization behaviour, it is difficult for some of them to establish a sense of presence on line⁵

⁵ Rena M. Palloff and Keith Pratt, Building Learning Communities in Cyberspace: Effective Strategies for the Online Classroom, (San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers, 1999), 10.

This need to socialize is patent in a Ping Pong Instant Message that I, as a tutor, received during the course from a student:

*“Hi! I think I’m being obsessed with the program, I want to be on line all the time too see if anybody enters. May be I will have to go to rehab when the introduction class is over... :)
Have a nice day!”*

This introductory course was not exclusively on line so we do not felt as crucial to have a specific place to students socialize and PIM’s can have this function, too. But we must refer that a place to talk about things, even not related with the course, must be available for the students.

Synchronous communication can be used in a formal way, in order to provide to the group a sense of working together in real time, by scheduling times to everyone goes on line. Due to accessibility to on line computers and some issues with the language it was not part of this introductory course to have meetings at real time.

Ping Pong has an integrated calendar that was used to schedule deadlines to the assignments and to remember students to work on final thesis project proposal during the semester. This calendar send PIM’s and emails to students and teachers automatically.

Besides this function, the system has it owns reminders in what concerns to new movements in the application. At first, was decided that the first page to appear to users entering in the LMS should be the summary of Content Menu section, in order to students could have a whole view of the course. But as the course was getting further, we decided that it was better that the general summary page appear, because in this page the user can see if there are new messages in the whole system.

Some considerations about why presentation and formatting of the contents is important and how can this give information to the student

The design of an on line course had several aspects that should be carefully reflected, in what concerns to format the contents. Ping Pong has an administration area very easy to manage, even by people who do not know anything about HTML.

The LMS settings allow choosing several things. We are going to point the most important in what concerns to design.

Ping Pong is a course manager that allows several different courses on the same application. Each course pops-up in the screen when clicked, so the first thing to make students and teachers aware is if they have the “allow pop-ups” option enabled in their browsers. Another option of the settings section is to choose what kind of resolution we want to this pop-up to

have. If we have information about resolution of computers of students and teachers we can setup this according to that, if not we can choose the smallest one [800x600]. Another issue is about the type of fonts. The most suitable fonts for the web or a screen are the sans-serif fonts, because they are the most readable, and Ping Pong allows choosing the type of the fonts as well.

Tutors and teachers can choose the first page to appear to users when they start Ping Pong course. In the first days, we selected the Content Menu section because it was important to students to be aware of the structure of the course, but after that we change this in order to the Menu section appears first. This is useful because when the course is running it is more important that the first page alerts the users to what is new and the Menu section of Ping Pong has this functionality. Every time a student or a teacher enters the course, he can see what sections had new information. For example, a student can see if there is some important message in Message Board or what Discussion Forums have new participations, and a teacher can see if there are new questions from students, etc.

In the administration of the Content Menu section, the course can be built with blocks of elements like Heading; Text; Link; Image; Sound; Video; HTML-code; etc. [Figure 3 of Attachment 2] This way, when the tutor or teacher inserts the element Heading, he just need to insert the text in the boxes. Then, the application will transform it into a formatted heading (with bold and larger font). Each one of these blocks has several options. The Heading block, for instance, has six types of headings and it can be centred, or aligned to the right or to the left.

Ping Pong has a type of block called HTML-code that is very important to mention because this allows more flexibility in the design of the course, if the tutor or the teacher has some knowledge of HTML language. We used this kind of block to insert spaces, to underline sentences, to create a table, to insert links inside the text and to highlight some words in the text.

Although the LMS accept all this kind of formatting it has some restrictions. For instance, if we need to insert a link and we use the block of elements Link, it will be displayed separated from the rest of the text and it will open inside Ping Pong.

We wanted to write hypertext⁶, not just insert text into online environment. As an example, if we are giving information about where a student can buy or get a book or an article, instead of giving the web address to the online store or to the library of university we just link the title of the book or the article to the online store or, if the material is online, to it directly. This can be done with text, pictures, videos or sounds.

⁶ The principle of Hypertext relies on the article “*As we may think*”, from 1945, by Vannevar Bush [<http://ccat.sas.upenn.edu/~jod/texts/vannevar.bush.html>] The author idealized Memex, a theoretical machine that it was supposed to work similar to the mental associations that we make when we think [<http://www.artmuseum.net/w2vr/timeline/Bush.html>]. The term Hypertext was coined in the sixties by Ted Nelson [<http://xanadu.com.au/ted/>], and according to the World Wide Web Consortium, “*is text which is not constrained to be linear. Hypertext is text which contains links to other texts*” [<http://www.w3.org/WhatIs.html>]

This raises another issue about usability that needs a little knowledge of HTML. If the page that we want to link is inside Ping Pong, we just need to insert a block of the element link or insert it with the HTML tag. But if the page that we want to link is outside Ping Pong, for instance the web page of the Library of University of Uppsala, we need to force the link to open in another window of the browser - we used the tag [target="_blank"] after the URL. This way, students and teachers will have always the Ping Pong page available at the same time they do research on libraries. This is particularly useful on Reading Lists that student must see at the same time he is searching for the books, the articles or the sites the teachers referenced. There is another issue with letting links to external pages opening inside Ping Pong: if we link to University of Uppsala website, for example, using an internal link tag, it will open inside the Ping Pong pop-up and once there, there is no back button like it will be in browser. This way the student and teacher could feel a little lost.

Conclusion

In this paper we described what we have done in order to design the introductory course of the master program "Roads to Democracy(ies)", using Ping Pong, a Learning Management System (LMS). We tried to justify the steps and the decisions we made with bibliography from other authors and we added some considerations about formatting and technical aspects that improve usability of a Learning Management System by teachers and students.

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[Attachment 1]

Roads to Democracy(ies)

A joint two year master program given by Uppsala University and Coimbra University

INTRODUCTORY COURSE

Week 41 (2005-10-10 – 2005-10-14)

Introduction

The introduction includes a presentation of the course and its teachers. You will be asked to provide an online presentation of yourself in order to learn how to work with the online system. This exercise serves two functions: 1) learning to use the on-line system Ping Pong, 2) getting to know your fellow students and the teachers.

You should try to post a picture of yourself and some basic background information (i.e. where you studied as undergraduate, what were your majors and minors, other interests, etc.). Assessment will be based on active participation in the exercise rather than on the technical quality of your presentation.

Weeks 42 and 43 (2005-10-17 – 2005-10-28)

Assignment Theme 1: Democracy in Sweden and Portugal Today

The purpose of the assignment is to develop an understanding of how democracy functions by studying how it works in practice in Sweden and Portugal. This exercise will also help you to acquire an understanding of how different institutions can support the development of democracy.

You are required to take a fairly simple on-line quiz. The quiz is not a test in the proper sense of the word. Its purpose is to provide you with basic information on how democracy in Sweden and Portugal functions today. Feel free to discuss your answers with your fellow students. Discussion Theme 2” will be open from 2005-10-17 to 2005-10-28. Assessment will be based on active participation rather than a test score on the quiz.

Weeks 44 and 45 (2005-10-31 – 2005-11-11)

Assignment Theme 2: Definitions of Democracy and Theories of Government

Within this thematic module you will develop an understanding of the theoretical debate on the idea of democracy and in particular the relationship between democracy and general theories of government.

*Using the suggested reading list as well as other library and internet resources attempt to discuss the following topics. The discussion forum “Discussion Theme 2” will be open from 2005-10-31 to 2005-11-11. You also will be expected to comment, once again using your available resources, on at least **one** of your fellow students’ contributions. Assessment will be based on the quality of the answers rather than on the number or length of your contributions. This is an open discussion so you need not worry about the grammatical correctness of your contributions. Just make it readable. Concentrate on content rather than form.*

- 1. Compare different definitions of democracy. Which definitions are most useful for comparative studies? Which definition of democracy is most commonly used today?**
- 2. Compare participatory democracy, social democracy and representative democracy.**
- 3. Discuss the relationship between democracy and conservatism, liberalism and socialism.**
- 4. Is there a gender issue regarding the interpretation of democracy? Discuss the empowerment of women and its relationship to democratisation.**

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Bobbio, Norberto, *Democracy And Dictatorship: The Nature And Limits Of State Power*. Cambridge: Polity Press 1997.

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[freedomhouse.org/century.pdf]

[<http://www.politicalresources.net/>]

Weeks 46 and 47 (2005-11-14 – 2005-11-25)

Assignment Theme 3: *The Development of Democracy*

Completion of this exercise will provide you with a broad knowledge of the spread of democracy and the historical development of democratic institutions. You will also obtain insights into the use of comparative methods in historical research. Assessment will be based on your ability to extract from the reading materials and other resources support for the answers to the discussion questions and/or your viewpoint in a discussion.

*Using the suggested reading list as well as other library and internet resources attempt to discuss the following topics. The discussion forum "Discussion Theme 3" will be open from 2005-11-14 to 2005-11-25. You also will be expected to comment, once again using your available resources, on at least **two** of your fellow students' contributions. Assessment will be based on the quality of the answers rather than on the number or length of your contributions. This is an open discussion so that you need not worry about grammatical correctness of your contributions. Concentrate on content rather than form.*

- 1. Discuss the breakdown of democratic rule and democratic institutions in inter-war Europe. What importance should be attached to economic, social and ideological factors? Why did fascism/national socialism and authoritarian governments replace democracy in several European countries?**
- 2. Discuss the spread of democracy. Which factors foster the spread of democracy? Which factors obstruct democratic development?**

3. Discuss how the measurement of democracy influences our perceptions of how it spreads. How could or how should democracy be measured?
4. What are “the three waves of democracy”?

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- [<http://vlib.org/>]
- [<http://www.riksdagen.se>]

Weeks 48 and 49 (2005-11-28 – 2005-12-09)

Assignment Theme 4: Democracy: Present Challenges

In this module you will acquire an understanding of how democracy is interpreted today as well as the ability to critically discuss current issues related to democracy in the contemporary world. Furthermore, you will obtain an understanding of the different challenges to the democratic idea, in particular the emergence of supranational levels of government and the interplay between national and European democratic developments. Assessment will be based on your ability to extract from the reading materials and other resources support for the answers to the discussion questions and/or your viewpoint in a discussion.

Using the suggested reading list as well as other library and internet resources attempt to discuss the following topics. The discussion forum "Discussion Theme 4" will be open from 2005-11-28 to 2005-12-09. Provide at topic for discussion, preferably one related to your thesis work. Comment on at least one of your fellow student's suggested topic for discussion, once again using your available resources. Assessment will be based on the quality of the answers rather than on the number or length of your contributions. This is an open discussion so that you need not worry about grammatical correctness of your contributions. Concentrate on content rather than form.

1. Is the European Union a democratic project? Discuss the relationship between local and regional democratic institutions and supra-national organisations.
2. Discuss the impact of globalisation on democracy.
3. Discuss the impact of terrorism on democracy.

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- Rohrschneider, Pobert, "The Democracy Deficit and Mass Support for an EU-Wide Government," *American Journal of Political Science*, Vol. 46, No. 2, (April 2002), 463-475.
[<http://www.jstor.org/>]

Weeks 50 through 2 (2005-12-12 – 2006-01-13)

Assignment *Thesis Project Proposal*

The planning, preparation and presentation of a well-developed thesis topic will improve your ability to comprehend and share specific points of view regarding democratic ideas, institutions and structures and to master the communication and knowledge sharing skills that support it. Assessment will be based on the content of the proposal (i.e. the review of previous related research, presentation of possible sources, grasp of theoretical considerations, the formulation of the research problem) as well as the quality of the written and oral presentation including discussing other students' proposals.

You should work on thesis proposal throughout the entire course. Using the preparatory work for each assignment as well as the related discussions you should develop a feasible research proposal. The topic should include a comparative approach so as to utilise the expertise of the participating institutions. This, of course, does not necessarily mean that comparisons must be made between Portugal and Sweden, but the comparative approach is emphasised. The proposal should have an approximate length of about 20-25 pages. It should focus on the problem you wish to investigate. You should clarify what is known about the problem in previous research, discuss from what perspective you wish to approach the problem (including theoretical considerations), consider what sources are available and which methods are most suitable for solving the research problem. The deadline for submission of the thesis proposal is 18:00 hrs 2006-01-15.

PLANNING FORM: Roads to Democracy(ies)

Type of course: **Introductory course**
 Name of module: **Introduction**
 Target group: **Master-level students**
 Level of unit: **First semester**
 Number of ECTS credits: **15 ECTS (notional student working time: 375 hours)**

Competences

1. Obtain a critical awareness of the relationship between current events and the processes of the past.
2. Obtain extensive skills in problem identification and solving, communication, and knowledge sharing.
3. Develop creative skills.
4. Acquire a concern for quality.
5. Become acquainted with the pedagogical tools of E-learning.
6. Acquire an ability to use computer and internet resources and techniques.

Learning Outcomes	Educational Activities	Estimated student work time in hours	Assessment
	<i>Presentation of Course</i>	2	
	<i>Learn to use web-based system Ping-Pong</i>	6	Self presentation (2%)
Acquire an understanding of how democracy works in practice.	<i>Democracy in Sweden and Portugal Today</i> Use internet and library resources	24	Quiz on democracy
Acquire an understanding of how different institutions can support the development of democracy	Take online quiz Web-based discussion of quiz	2 4	 (8%)

Learning Outcomes	Educational Activities	Estimated student work time in hours	<i>Assessment</i>
Acquire an understanding of the theoretical debate on the democratic idea, namely on the relationship between democracy and general theories of government.	<i>Definitions of Democracy and Theories of Government</i> Use of internet and library resources Web-based discussions Written paper Preparation for discussion seminar Discussion of papers	30 5 5 5 2	Participation in web-based discussions (10%)
Obtain a broad knowledge of the historical development of democratic institutions. Obtain insights into the use of comparative methods in historical research.	<i>The Development of Democracy</i> Use internet and library resources Web-based discussions Written paper Preparation for discussion seminar Discussion of papers	30 5 5 5 2	Participation in web-based discussions (10%)
Acquire an understanding of democracy today as well as the ability to critically discuss current issues related to democracy in the contemporary world. Obtain an understanding of different challenges to the democratic idea, in particular the emergence of supranational levels of government and the interplay between national and European democratic developments.	<i>Democracy: Present Challenges</i> Use internet and library resources Web-based discussions Written paper Preparation for discussion seminar Discussion of papers	30 5 5 5 2	Participation in web-based discussions (10%)
Obtain the capability to comprehend and share specific points of view regarding democratic ideas, institutions and structures and to master the communication and knowledge sharing skills that	<i>Thesis Project Proposal</i> Use internet and library resources Web-based discussions Write thesis proposal	100 4 70	Written thesis proposal; Participation in discussion

support it	Reading of thesis proposals and preparation for discussion	25	seminar
	Discussion of thesis proposals in seminars	10	
	Course evaluation	1	(60%)
		389	100%

The course is web-based expect for the discussion of the thesis proposals which takes place in a series of real-life seminars.

[Attachment 2]

https://pingpong.uu.se - Introduction: Roads to Democracy(ies) - PING PONG® - Mozilla Firefox

ACTIVITY ZONE

How to fill in your profile

1. Click on the "My Profile" tab in the main page of Ping Pong:

2. You must fill in the information you want to provide. Then you must click on **browse** button at your right side to search for your picture in your computer (Note that pictures must have 80x100 px). When you have finished just click on the **save** button.

Content menu

- ▷ Introduction
- **Assignment 1 - Learn to use web-based system Ping-Pong**
- ▷ Assignment 2 - Democracy in Sweden and Portugal Today
- ▷ Assignment 3 - Definitions of Democracy and Theories of Government
- ▷ Assignment 4 - The Development of Democracy
- ▷ Assignment 5 - Democracy: Present Challenges
- Assignment 6 - Thesis Project Proposal
- Assignment 7 - Evaluation
- Evaluation Form

pingpong.uu.se

[Figure 1]

https://pingpong.uu.se - Introduction: Roads to Democracy(ies) - PING PONG® - Mozilla Firefox

ACTIVITY ZONE

Howto view students and teachers profile in Ping Pong

- To view students and teachers profiles, you need to click in:

- Then you must click on **Participants**:

ACTIVITY ZONE

CONTACT

- Contact**
- MESSAGE BOARD**
- FAQ**
- DISCUSSION**
- PARTICIPANTS**
- SEND MESSAGE**
- ANSWER QUESTIONS**
- PROJECT GROUPS**
- PIM**

- In the right side of the next page there is a box where you can chose **participants**, to view the students or **Trainers**, to view the teachers:

ACTIVITY ZONE

PARTICIPANTS

People online in Introduction: Roads to Democracy(ies)

Avatar	Name	Profile	Email
	Last name	Profile	Email
	Berto Simões	Paula Sofia	psimoes@esec.pt

SELECT LIST

Persons online

pingpong.uu.se

[Figure 2]

[Figure 3]